

EVALUATION OF THE OUT-OF-PLANE PROPERTIES OF 3D-KNITTED FABRIC COMPOSITES.

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ABSTRACT

3D-knitted composites are being investigated as a sandwich material, especially for complex double-curved surfaces. The new material differs from existing knitted fabric composites in its open and three-dimensional structure. Currently, the impact and bending properties are being examined.

Although the original material has good properties already, some improvements to the original knitting concept have been made. By inserting extra yarns into the skins of the fabric, the bending stiffness can be increased significantly, while the use of composite yarns can further improve the mechanical behaviour; it makes impregnation easier as well.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composites based on knittings have recently received somewhat more attention because of the very good drapability of the knitting before curing and because of the possibility of forming complex shapes with a reduced number of processing steps. [1]

The new type of composite presented in this paper can however hardly be compared with previous ones. It differs from other composites through the extremely open structure that is more or less that of the 3D-knitting itself.

Production of these 3D-knittings is very similar to that of flat knittings. The top and bottom skin of the knitted sandwich structure are simultaneously knitted on a double bed Raschel knitting machine, on two different bars. Each bar is equipped with its own set of needles. And since the two sets of needles can be programmed independent of each other, two different skin structures can be obtained if desired. Weft-knitting of these structures is impossible due to the specific nature of the 3D-knittings. An advantage of the warp-knitting process is the high production volumes. However, setting up a new knitting or experimenting with new types or techniques is extremely time consuming, while the use of new yarns poses some additional problems.

During the knitting proces, the two skins are connected to each other by means of pile fibers. These fibers are part of both skins, but they switch regularly from one bar to the other. In this way, one obtains an integrally knitted fabric where the pile fibers act as spacers between the two sides of the sandwich structure. By adjusting the distance between the two bars, one can change

the thickness of the fabric and hence, some of the basic mechanical properties of the fabric and the composite.

For the moment, only hexagonal and rhombic cell structures are being produced : in these 3D-knits, the piles form a hexagonal or rhombic "honeycomb core" structure, while the skins show an open hexagonal or rhombic framework (fig.1). In this way, a highly deformable sandwich structure with good ventilation properties can be formed. However, it is also possible to knit almost completely closed surfaces. This possibility is welcomed if one wants to produce composite parts that have a smooth surface on the outer side. In this case, it is not necessary any more to laminate an extra top skin. Delamination problems are avoided and the number of processing steps is minimized.

Figure 1. Rhombic (R7) and hexagonal (H10) 3D-knittings.

Up till now, most problems with sandwich structures arise when the skins delaminate from the core. This is particularly the case when the sandwich structure has been damaged or has been impacted by some object. Regarding this problem, 3D-knittings can provide an alternative to conventional sandwich structures while the integrally knitted structure prevents the skins from delaminating. The same advantage can be obtained with 3D-woven composites due to their integrally woven structure [2]; however, it is difficult to deform these structures in a double-curved shape.

2. MATERIAL

Two different knitting structures have been tested so far. The knitting R7 has a rhombic unit cell (7.2x3.9 mm; 6.3 mm high) and H10 has hexagonal cells (9.7x6.3 mm; 5.7 mm high) (Fig. 1). These 3D-knitted textiles can be impregnated in several ways. High viscosity epoxy resins such as the Hexcel R2503 resin (20% solvent) are applied by hand, while low viscosity epoxies like Ciba-Geigy LZ5021 (50% solvent) can be used for continuous impregnation in a resin bath. The two epoxy resins are both cured at 125°C in a hot press under displacement control. The Hexcel resin is cured for 60 min, while the Ciba-Geigy resin is cured during 25 min.

Multi layered specimens can be produced by co-curing several prepregs or by adhesively bonding separately cured 3D-knitted composites, but co-curing gives the best results. In the same way, additional 2D-knitted skins can be added if required.

Foamed 3D-knitted structures can be fabricated rather easily by placing the cured panels between two preheated aluminum plates. A PU-foam mixture is then poured into the panel to expand.

3. NEW YARNS

For the moment, all 3D-knittings are based on plain PET-monofilaments whose intrinsic stiffness is responsible for keeping the two skins apart. Hence, they constitute the real skeleton of the knitting. This means of course that it will not be possible to replace the monofilaments entirely by i.e. glass rovings which are more interesting considering the mechanical properties of the final composite. One of the main problems with PET is that the monofilaments are rather difficult to impregnate with epoxy resin due to the bad wetting properties of epoxy on knittable PET-monofilaments. This can clearly be seen in figure 2 which shows that only droplets are formed onto the monofilament. Because of this, the mechanical properties will be less than the maximum attainable. In order to obtain a good impregnation of the pile fibers a lot of resin is needed. The major drawback is however that the composite gets rather heavy then.

Figure 2. Bad impregnation of PET-monofilaments with epoxy resin.

To solve this problem several types of composite yarn can be used. They all consist of a central PET-monofilament surrounded by many shorter yarns that are also much thinner. The extra yarns could be i.e. bicombed polyester, ramie-viscose, polyamide-polyester or others (see fig.3). With such types of yarn, a much better and a more homogenous impregnation is obtained since the resin is absorbed by the cavities between the yarns (see fig. 4).

Figure 3. The polyamide-polyester yarn (75x).

Figure 4. Homogenous impregnation of composite pile fibers with epoxy resin.

Another advantage of combined yarns is that for a specific yarn thickness, PET-monofilaments with a reduced section can be used. The combined yarn is much more flexible so that the knitting process is less restricted. Up to now, the knitting geometry and unit cell size were determined by the diameter of the PET-monofilament or otherwise stated by the stiffness of the monofilament. So, it was not possible for example to produce 3D-knittings with small cells and thick yarns. With the new yarns, production is more versatile.

4. BASIC PROPERTIES

4.1. COMPRESSION STRENGTH

Compression strength depends for the greater part on the properties of the core. This includes the properties of the pile fibers, their impregnation and the presence of foam. For the knitted composites without foam, it is clear that the material will fail when the pile fibers buckle and will hence be related to the resin content of the impregnated pile fibers. A typical load-displacement curve is shown in fig. 5a : after an initial linear elastic behaviour, the pile fibers collapse and the compression strength is reduced significantly. Ultimately, the compression strength increases because of densification.

In fig. 5b the same material has been tested with this exception that it has been foamed. No pile fibers collapse because the foam takes over the load on the critical moment.

Figure 5. Typical load-displacement curves showing pile yarn collapse (a) and no pile yarn collapse because of the foam (b). (ASTM C 365-75)

To situate our material, a comparison has been made in fig.6 with 3D-woven composites, Nomex honeycomb (cell size 1/8") and PMI-foam. The knitted composites compare well to the 3D-woven ones (about 2/3 of the strength) and to the PMI-foam (equal strength). But it is still inferior to Nomex honeycomb-based sandwich panels (only 1/2 the strength).

Figure 6. Comparison of specific flat compression strength.

4.2. IMPACT RESISTANCE

One of the most promising aspects of the new composite material is the good impact resistance. In fig.8, results are shown of tests on 3-layered knitted composites with hexagonal unit cells that have been subjected to an impact test with a spherical impactor ($\varnothing=60\text{mm}$, mass=3.125kg) on a solid support. In this figure, the maximum deceleration that is reached during an impact test is plotted for a low and a high resin content. The lower the maximum deceleration when testing on a solid support, the better the material. Simplified, this can be explained as follows : when an impact test is carried out on two different materials under the same conditions, the material with the highest deceleration will have to bear a very high force during a short time. The material with the lower deceleration has to bear a much smaller force but during a longer time.

Impact is controlled by a whole set of parameters. In the first place, it is controlled by the geometry of the knitting where the height of the fabric and the pile fiber density are important. The height of the fabric is directly related to the buckling resistance of the pile fibers. It is clear that the pile fibers support the structure and should hence be stiff enough. This was one of the main problems during the first tests with pure PET monofilaments¹ impregnated with epoxy resin. The pile fibers could not be impregnated homogeneously because of bad wetting properties of the epoxy resin on PET.

A second parameter is the unit cell geometry (hexagonal, rhombic, ...). This influence can probably be traced back to the pile fiber density. Regarding this, it is interesting to note that when pile fibers are close to each other or when the resin content of the composite is high, "walls" can be formed. These walls are films of resin that are formed between adjacent pile fibers; they give the composite extra strength. The higher the resin content of the composite, the more walls are being formed. However, the use of too much resin is not recommended since the composite gets heavier and can become more brittle.

In fig.7 a comparison is made between the hexagonal and rhombic knitted composite. The influence of the number of layers is presented as well. The R7 material is always slightly better than H10. This can be explained by the higher pile fiber density and the higher skin density in

¹ high tenacity PETp from Hoechst, $\varnothing=0.1\text{mm}$

R7. There also seems to be no relevant difference between samples with more than four layers of knitting.

Figure 7. Comparison between hexagonal and rhombic knitted composites and polyesterene. Influence of the number of layers in the knitted composite. (Resin : 70w% Hexcel R2503)

The resin content is a third parameter for the impact resistance. The influence of this parameter can be clearly seen in fig.8. Deceleration may not be too high for applications such as shock protection (like helmets). So, in fig.8, the sample with the high resin content has a better performance because the pile fibers have been reinforced more, leading to a lower deceleration.

Figure 8. Influence of the resin content for impact tests on solid support. Material : 3 layers of H10 ; resin : Hexcel R2503.

4.3. BENDING PROPERTIES

From classical sandwich theory, we expect the bending properties to be influenced mainly by the stiffness of the skins and the distance between them.

In order for the sandwich effect to take place, the skins must be separated by a minimum distance. The pile fibers have to maintain this distance during bending and for this reason, the buckling resistance of the pile fibers must be high. Also the core should have a high shear resistance. This means of course that the impregnation must be good and also homogenous. From paragraph 3.2 we know that sometimes "walls" are formed and these are very efficient to enlarge the shear resistance of the core.

In fig.9, the anisotropy in the flexural stiffness of H10 is shown. All 3-point bending tests are performed according ASTM D 790M-86. The flexural stiffness of the sandwich structure is about three times higher in the length direction compared to that of the width direction. This anisotropy is a direct consequence of the rib structure in the skins and the presence of "walls". These walls have a big influence on the shear properties. For the hexagonal material, most walls and also the most ribs are oriented in the length direction and thus that direction has the highest

stiffness. They act as stiffeners in that direction. For the rhombic material (R7), the orientation distribution of the ribs is more homogenous.

Figure 9. Anisotropy in flexural stiffness of hexagonal 3D-knitted fabric. (H10, 70 w% Hexcel R2503)

In fig. 7 a comparison is made between between some 3D-knitted structures, PMI-foam and polypropylene-honeycomb to situate the new material. Its remarkable that the geometry of the knitting can have such a big influence on the properties (H10 and R7).

Figure 10. Comparison of the flexural stiffness of different core materials.
(Knitted composites : Hexcel R2503 resin)

To improve the strength and stiffness of the skins that carry a large part of the load, some extra material can be incorporated. In this way a higher fiber volume fraction can be reached in the skins, leading to a better performance.

Another advantage of the extra yarns worked into the skins is that when different layers of knitting have to be laminated, the contact area between adjacent layers is much larger compared to the original knitting structure.

5. APPLICATIONS

The new composite presented in this paper has a bright future as material for applications that need a combination of good ventilation, high impact resistance and flexural stiffness. The highly deformable knitting (and prepreg) is another advantage too.

One application where this is demonstrated clearly, is the bicycle helmet. With 3D-knitted composites it is possible to produce a bicycle helmet with improved cooling capacity compared to other commercial helmets. This is something that has been waited for for a long time.

Another application could be radar domes for aircraft because it is possible with these 3D-knitted fabrics to produce a light, stiff and double-curved sandwich structure. Since the knitting is very deformable, the dome can be deep drawn and hence, production is not complicated.

More general, whenever double-curved sandwich structures are needed, the 3D-knits can provide a cost efficient alternative to honeycomb sandwich materials.

6. CONCLUSIONS

1. A new type of composite sandwich structure, based on a double layer knitted fabric has been developed.
2. This new concept has some advantages such as :
 - a flexural stiffness similar to PMI-foams
 - flat compression strength similar to PMI-foams
 - impact energy absorption capability similar to polystyrene foams
 - ventilation capacity superior to other structural shells or sandwich structures
3. Exciting new applications are possible :
 - alternative core material with excellent drapability
 - alternative shell for helmets
 - medical applications
4. The use of composite yarns can further improve the mechanical properties.

7. REFERENCES

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MECHANICAL PROPERTIES: TIME DEPENDENT EFFECTS
